

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THERE IS A PLACE FOR EVERYONE IN EDUCATION: THE IMPORTANCE OF AN INCLUSIVE APPROACH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION STRENGTH

Ibrahimova S.

*Sheki branch of the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Honored Teacher,
Senior Lecturer*

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8944-3611>

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Abstract

The article examines the process of organizing training in inclusive education in Azerbaijan, the implementation of laws adopted in this area, factors to be taken into account in organizing inclusive education in preschool institutions, types of inclusive education applied in preschool institutions, the related work of specialists working with children with disabilities involved in inclusive education, the importance of child-centered pedagogy in implementing inclusive education, determining the time of a child's involvement in inclusive education, the results of implemented state programs, as well as ways to overcome the difficulties encountered. The adopted program on inclusive education reflects the main task of working with parents of children in need of special care, active participation of the public in this area, ensuring the education of such children in disadvantaged families, meeting their spiritual needs, providing them with the opportunity to receive training together with their typical peers, and at the same time helping them to form themselves as active members of society. The article presents other problems related to inclusive education, including the implementation of special programs for children with disabilities, the cooperation of teachers with the parents of these children in inclusive groups, the usefulness of parents' participation in the learning process, the support provided to teachers by parents, etc.

Keywords: inclusive education, discrimination, disability, psycho-medical, sociological, psycho-medical, sociological, organizational, health opportunities, special care, psychologist, speech therapist, defectologist, intellectual, democratic values.

Interpretation of materials obtained during the research process.

In modern times, inclusive education means ensuring the right of persons with disabilities to education on an equal basis with other persons at all levels of education and creating an environment without barriers for their education. The aim of inclusive education is to ensure effective learning by involving children in the same school and class with their peers, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other characteristics. Inclusive education prevents any form of discrimination against children, and gives children the opportunity to receive excellent education and achieve success. When children with disabilities grow up with other peers and participate in the learning process, they develop a sense of mutual understanding and respect. [2;105].

Historically, inclusive education has been defined as the inclusion of children with special needs in regular schools [Mitchell D. 2008]; [Dukes C., & Lamar-Dukes P. 2006]. The concept of "special needs" or "disability" has been a central concept in the inclusive education process, and this concept is still gaining new concepts that interpret "special needs" from different aspects. Educational research, as well as educational approaches, have gone through three main stages of evolution, which differ from each other in their specific paradigmatic structure: psycho-medical, sociological and organizational paradigms. In the early stages of education for children with disabilities, the psycho-medical paradigm was a dominant factor in attitudes and beliefs, where medical and psychological traditions were quite clear. The psycho-medical paradigm

conceptualizes difficulties arising from deficiencies in the neurological or psychological state of the child. [9;71].

Inclusive education is an educational approach that supports all students to learn together, taking into account individual and other differences, and providing appropriate support and educational services according to their needs. In inclusive education, it is important that all students learn together and that every student is expected to participate in lessons, activities and learning opportunities. Teachers should organize all activities taking into account children with typically developing and special needs; they develop plans in collaboration with other experts and organizations to best meet the needs of all children and their needs. In this context, inclusive education is not only about disabled children; it aims to include all disadvantaged children and children with special needs, such as children with different mother tongues and children from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds.

Inclusive education is achieved through knowledge and experiences gained through normalization, generalization and integration practices based on the principle of equal opportunities. On the path to inclusive education, normalization is an approach that advocates that all children with special educational needs have access to educational services that are as close as possible to those enjoyed by their peers in the general population. Inclusion is defined as placing children with special educational needs in different groups in preschool educational institutions, making necessary adjustments in the physical environment to suit their needs, and participating in

classes and group activities with minimal assistance. Inclusion broadly encompasses all disadvantaged children, including those with special educational needs.

The following factors should be taken into account when organizing inclusive education in preschool institutions:

1. Preparation of an activity plan taking into account the characteristics of the child;
2. Conducting individual and group exercises that are of great importance in improving the initiative and teamwork skills of children with disabilities;
3. Observing the child's mental state before and after the session;
4. Developing motor skills through special gymnastics, games, and tasks;
5. Achieving active participation of children in events;
6. Developing children's abilities and talents.

In preschool institutions, groups in inclusive education are also formed based on the following principle: 2/3 of the children's collective are healthy children, and 1/3 are children with disabilities.

The following types of inclusive education are applied in preschool institutions:

1. Point access;
2. Partial access;
3. Full inclusion.

In point-based inclusion, preschool children with disabilities join the group of healthy children at certain times, for example, during walks, games or festive events. In partial inclusion, preschool children with disabilities do not spend the whole day in the group, but directly participate in physical education, fine arts and music classes. In full inclusion, children with disabilities participate in the inclusive group, like their healthy peers, all day and in all classes and events. Preschool education is important for all children. It is especially useful for children with disabilities. Inclusive education in preschool institutions should be optimally organized as follows:

1. Individual sessions with specialists - psychologists, speech therapists and defectologists;
2. Walking in specially equipped spaces is created taking into account the psychophysical capabilities of children with disabilities;
3. Frontal exercises are organized for the purpose of understanding and solving social tasks;

4. Conducting joint creative and constructive tasks and games in parent-child groups;

5. Organizing festive events, excursions and trips to create a positive mood and promote emotional development;

6. Strengthening eating, daytime sleep, and self-care habits – all of these

In addition to the principles on which it is based, the inclusive education approach also includes some features. Thus, the inclusive education approach requires the search for optimal opportunities to meet various requirements covering mental and physical capabilities and to take into account diversity. This approach not only responds to the interests of learners with different levels of interest and ability, but also encourages the professional development of those involved. The diversity of teaching methods also allows children to reveal their creative potential and stimulate their problem-solving skills in various ways.

In addition, inclusive education is also characterized by democratic values. Thus, inclusion implies ensuring the rights of all children to participate in education, to express their opinions, to participate in a quality educational process and to achieve certain results regardless of their personal, social and ethnic characteristics, and to provide support to children who may be subject to social exclusion, as well as those with poor attendance.

In educational institutions where inclusive education is applied, all students, including children with disabilities, have equal rights; the educational process is accessible to each child, they are provided with equal opportunities for communication; the learning process is efficiently organized, the pedagogical workers involved in the process have acquired the appropriate skills; the program takes into account the needs of each child, and families actively participate in the life of the educational institution. Thus, inclusive education can be characterized as a process in which all individuals, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other characteristics, receive education in the same educational institutions as their peers. They help overcome communicative barriers. [10;15].

The following scheme shows children with disabilities involved in inclusive education.

The related work of working professionals is noted.

In order to identify and eliminate the learning difficulties of children with disabilities in kindergartens, the management of the preschool educational institution, psychologist, defectologist, speech therapist, educator-teacher, assistants, and parents should work together as a team. The knowledge of educators-teachers and parents in the field of inclusion should be increased by using internal resources. Both individual and collective forms of work should be used to solve learning difficulties.

An improperly organized educational environment can aggravate the condition of a child with special needs. Special attention should be paid to the development of the following qualities in students in groups with an inclusive education component:

- Development of the emotional sphere;
- Development of the cognitive sphere;
- Development of stress tolerance;
- Development of self-confidence;
- Development of a positive attitude towards the real world and the ability to accept others;
- Development of independence;
- Development of self-determination, self-improvement and motivation.

Research shows that when preschool children with special needs are included in regular groups with the necessary support, they feel a sense of belonging to the team and have many opportunities to positively interact with them because they feel a sense of belonging to the team.

The educator-teacher should consider the following when establishing the training process:

1. By giving children various tasks, including children with special needs in the same types of activities;
2. Complete tasks together with the group;

3. Using other strategic ways of participating in the collective - games, field research, etc.

The number of children in groups in a special preschool educational institution is determined as follows:

	1-3 yaşadək	3-7 yaşadək
kor uşaqlar	6	6
zəifgörən, çəpgöz və ambliopiyalı uşaqlar	6	6
kar uşaqlar	6	6
zəifəşidən uşaqlar	6	8
nitqi ümumən inkişaf etməyən uşaqlar	6	10
kəkələyən uşaqlar	-	10
nitqi fonetik cəhətdən inkişaf etməyən uşaqlar	-	12
əqli cəhətdən geri qalan uşaqlar	6	6
dayaq-hərəkət aparatının funksiyalarının pozuntuları olan uşaqlar	6	6
mürəkkəb çatışmazlıqları olan uşaqlar	-	6

Determining the time for a child to be involved in inclusive education is also a complex issue. Thus, the integration of children with mild physical and mental disabilities should begin at preschool age. It is more expedient to mass integrate children with serious vision, hearing, speech and intellectual impairments after they have undergone special training. The training of children with severe and complex (complex) disabilities is possible only in special institutions. Inclusive education should begin in special groups operating within preschool institutions. Here, children with special needs come into contact with their normal peers during extracurricular activities and gradually get used to these conditions. Then these children are integrated into a regular group. Such a transition increases the circle of communication of children with special needs and accelerates the child's development. At the same time, it creates conditions for overcoming adaptation difficulties.

60% of children with disabilities can be educated in preschool and general education institutions without any adaptation, and 80-90% with minor adaptation (e.g., teaching strategy education, child-to-child support, and environmental adaptation). There is no evidence to support the argument that all children with disabilities have the same needs. There is also no solid evidence that children with disabilities require special strategies that differ significantly from regular teaching strategies. At times, the curriculum may need to be adjusted for some children and the communication mode may be different. However, all children have the right to benefit from the same curriculum and learn with the same socially constructive approaches.[14;19] Early childhood programs should be individualized for children with disabilities. When making decisions about individualized programs for children with special needs, pedagogical teams should understand the child's relationship to the environment, the early childhood program, and other environments. Knowledge can be gained from conversations with people who regularly observe and interact with children in those settings. The

nature of those interactions (e.g., how children approach tasks, how they perform, and how the environment responds to them) is an important part of the information needed to plan programs that are beneficial to children with disabilities.

In inclusive groups, the teacher's cooperation with the parents of these children is especially important. Cooperation with parents means their participation in the teacher's assessment of the child, determining his or her developmental levels, participation in the learning process, and a systematic approach to achieving the child's next developmental goals. In fact, parental participation in the learning process is important not only for children with disabilities, but also for children without disabilities of various ages, in their acquisition of the necessary academic and life skills.

3 ways in which parental involvement in the learning process is beneficial:

1. For the teacher – building relationships with parents, moral support for the teacher, and the school environment;
2. For the child – improved behavior, attitude, intellectual development, and attendance at classes;
3. For parents – increased parental self-confidence, parental satisfaction, and their own interest in education.

Support provided by parents includes the following:

1. Providing information – parents provide complete information about their child (strengths and weaknesses, medical conditions), are in constant communication with teachers and specialists, and participate in updating the FTP that meets the needs of their child. Parents also feel that they are being listened to and that the school cares about their child;

2. Collaboration – Parents should not only provide information, but also assist the teacher in preparing classroom assignments at home in advance, in adapting the home environment to the needs of the children, and in achieving the goals in the FTP;

3. Resources – Parents can also be closely involved in helping the teacher prepare certain learning tools. Others can participate as teaching assistants and participate in the implementation of certain activities and the implementation of certain areas of the curriculum.

Support for parents includes:

1. Communication – Information about their children should be accessible to parents. They should be aware of the difficulties their children are facing and what the educational institution is trying to do to address them. The teacher should communicate with parents through various means (in-person meetings, home visits, weekly or daily reports, telephone, e-mail, text messages).

2. Education - parents feel the need to be informed about how to deal with their children with disabilities, their participation or role in the learning process. One effective way to educate parents is through guidance for parents that promotes their children's development and discussing issues that concern them.

3. Support. Sometimes parents just need to be heard and want the teacher to simply be a good listener.

To promote children's health, toys, objects, activities, and interactions with adults must be properly determined, while regulating children's nutritional desires and activities.

The educator-teacher or specialist working in the inclusive education system must also receive integrative education and have integrative knowledge. The main result of the education of children with disabilities covered by the inclusive education system is the creation of an excellent system of knowledge, skills and habits in them. [13;46] The transition to inclusive education reveals a number of psychological problems that require solutions. In addition to children with disabilities, inclusive education gives a lot to healthy children. Joint education provides healthy children with a sense of being more tolerant of the mental and physical shortcomings of their peers, and the formation of a sense of openness and readiness for mutual cooperation. In children with disabilities, inclusive education ensures the formation of a positive attitude towards their peers, adequate social behavior, full realization of potential opportunities in development and education. Timely assistance allows you to mitigate the features observed in children with disabilities, and even in some cases completely eliminate them. This ensures their socialization and integration into society.

Child-centered pedagogy is essential in implementing inclusive education. All teachers encounter children with very different background knowledge, skills, interests and learning needs. Since there is no specific pedagogy for teaching children with disabilities, teachers in inclusive settings use child-centered pedagogy to meet the needs of all children. In a more traditional setting or more teacher-centered pedagogy, the teacher stands in front of the whole class, arranges the desks in rows and columns, passes on all the knowledge to the children and tells them whether their answers are right or wrong. This is what a good and instructive teacher should be like - this is what we

are taught. Child-centered pedagogy means putting children first and focusing on their needs, skills, interests and learning styles, and the teacher playing a supportive role in the learning process. In a child-centered approach, children without disabilities also look at them with surprise and react differently when they encounter a child with disabilities in one place or another. The main reason for this is the lack of communication and cooperation between them.

As a result, they do not understand each other and do not understand what they are feeling. In order to eliminate such problems, in modern times, as a result of international cooperation and a scientific approach, general effective directions for the implementation of inclusive education have been developed as a necessary stage in the development of humanity. Currently, in many countries of the world (Great Britain, the USA, Switzerland, etc.), children with disabilities study in general schools and go to kindergartens along with other peers. The responsibility for preparing children with disabilities for education together with their peers without disabilities essentially falls more on teachers, educators and psychologists. In general, it is intended that they adapt to education more quickly and communicate effectively with children. For example, in kindergartens or educational institutions where preschool preparation is conducted, the main role of educators is to develop collectivism, work habits, behavior, ethical and moral qualities in children, to create initial ideas about the world, and to carry out other functions. In short, in the process of school preparation, the teacher prepares the child for conscious activity in accordance with the tasks set by society, both physically and morally. The most important thing for effectiveness is the behavior of the teacher. In modern times, international and local legal documents require that children in need of special care be treated not as patients, but as people with disabilities. This forms a social approach to children in need of special care. The social model creates conditions for children with disabilities to properly use all their rights in order to develop their skills. Until now, the integration of children with disabilities into society has been limited on the basis of the medical model. A medical approach to a child in need of special care means a child with disabilities, a problem in terms of the medical model. In the past, children with disabilities were viewed through the prism of their violations, forced to undergo mandatory "treatments", institutionalization, and isolation from society. Sometimes such children were even deprived of life. Today, high-tech solutions, medications, and therapy methods are more constructive (for example, hearing aids for children with hearing impairments). Within the framework of this model, children in need of special care are expected to adapt more to society and their environment. It is forgotten that these children have the right to be accepted as they are. Often, they try to integrate them into the environment they find themselves in.

Conclusion

Effective organization of training in inclusive education leads to the conclusion that the value of a person should not depend on his abilities and

achievements, because everyone has the ability to feel, think and have the right to communicate. True education can only exist in the context of real relationships. Society must understand that all people need the support and friendship of their peers. The diversity of people should help develop all areas of life, it should not be an obstacle for them, but a means of overcoming existing obstacles. The main goal of inclusive education is to serve to ensure the continuous education and development of people with disabilities.

In conclusion, it can be noted that in modern society, in order to involve people with disabilities in the effective teaching and learning process, it is necessary to carry out educational and informative work at the public level, to form public awareness, to change public opinion in an unambiguously positive direction towards people with disabilities, as well as to create a favorable and safe environment. For this, first of all, the intelligentsia of society should not demonstrate a neutral or passive position towards the assimilation of people with disabilities. The problem of people with disabilities should be perceived by those around them as a social obligation, people should not show passive tolerance towards them, and discrimination should be eliminated. If the principles mentioned above are followed, it is possible to easily achieve the involvement of people with disabilities in education and their adaptation to society. The teaching and learning environment created thanks to the joint efforts and cooperation of teachers with parents can provide sufficient support to people with disabilities, and the implementation of new teaching strategies in this direction can increase the efficiency of education, further improve the learning process, and thus improve the learning outcomes of students. The creation of teacher learning communities in educational institutions will create a foundation for more effective organization of group activities, collaboration and communication skills with individuals with disabilities.

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